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Preparation of Some Thiazolidinone and Their Benzoyl Derivatives and Study of Their Antimicrobial Activity

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Manuscript received 10 March 1982, revised 10 November 1983,
accepted 27 February 1984

PHENOLS possess antiseptic¹, germicidal², anti-fungal³, antibacterial and other biological activities. 4-Thiazolidinones are also associated with various biological activities⁴⁻⁷. 4-Thiazolidinones of type (I) containing phenol residue were obtained by the action of thioglycolic acid, thiolactic acid or thiomalic acid on Schiff bases which in their turn were obtained by the reaction of 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzophenone⁸ with different sulpha drugs. The constitution was supported by ir spectra^{9-11,12}. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

I

R = H, 4'-methyl pyrimidyl, 4',6'-dimethyl pyrimidyl, 2'-thiazolyl, 3',4'-dimethyl oxazolyl.

R₁ = H, OH, CH₃, COOH.

R₂ = H, COC₆H₅.

R₃ = H, Br.

IR spectra :

The ir spectra of 4-thiazolidinones (I) were taken on KBr pellets. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ was obtained at 1640 and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{CO})$ at 1590, $\nu(\text{phenolic}-\text{OH})$ at 3410 and $\nu(\text{NHSO}_2)$ at 1150 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

*Preparation of α -phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzalanil/2-benzoate*¹⁴ : 2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzophenone (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol was added to sulphanilamide (0.01 mol) in ethanol and refluxed on a waterbath for 6 h and the content poured into water. The product was isolated

and crystallised from ethanol. The anils were benzoylated by the treatment of benzoyl chloride and 10% cold sodium hydroxide solution. The product (R₂ = H) was poured on ice, separated and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 86°, yield 80% (Found : C, 53.90 ; H, 3.76 ; N, 6.22. C₂₀H₁₇O₂N₂SBr requires C, 53.93 ; H, 3.82 ; N, 6.29%).

Similarly, other anils were prepared by condensing ketones with sulphadimidine, sulphamethazine, sulphathiazole and sulphaoxazoles. Their benzoyl derivatives were also prepared.

Preparation of α -phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methyl phenyl)-3-p-amino sulphophenyl-4-thiazolidinone : α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzalanil/2-benzoate (0.01 mol) in benzene was refluxed with thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) on a water bath for 4 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 93°, yield 72% (Found : C, 50.81 ; H, 3.23 ; N, 5.33. C₂₂H₁₆O₄N₂S₂Br requires C, 50.86 ; H, 3.28 ; N, 5.39%).

Similarly, other anils and their benzoyl derivatives were treated with thioglycolic acid.

Preparation of α -phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methyl phenyl)-3-p-aminosulphophenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone : Thiolactic acid (0.01 mol) was added to a solution of α -phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzal anil (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 76°, yield 61% (Found : C, 57.71 ; H, 3.90 ; N, 5.22. C₂₈H₂₁O₄N₂S₂Br requires C, 57.78 ; H, 3.94 ; N, 5.25%).

Similarly, other anils and their benzoyl derivatives were treated with thiolactic acid.

Preparation of α -phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methyl phenyl)-3-p-aminosulphophenyl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone : α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzal anil (0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 30 min (Reddellien method¹³). The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate and reprecipitated with acid and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 70°, yield 58% (Found : C, 49.79 ; H, 3.58 ; N, 4.79. C₂₄H₂₁O₆N₂S₂Br requires C, 49.91 ; H, 3.64 ; N, 4.85%).

Similarly, other anils and their benzoyl derivatives were treated with thiomalic acid.

Antimicrobial screening :

The purified products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup plate method¹⁵ using *S. aureus* (gram +ive) and *E. coli* (gram -ive). Ethanolic solutions of the compounds were used for the tests. The zones of inhibition for the test solution containing 0.5 mg of the compound were recorded. The anils are active* against *S. aureus* and moderately active to inactive against *E. coli*. Most of the 4-thiazolidinones are highly active* against *S. aureus* but are inactive against *E. coli*.

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* Details of activity tests may be obtained from the author on request.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar, for research facilities and Junior Research Fellowship to two of them (S. V. P. and J. N. V.).

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Chemical Investigation of *Ougeinia dalbergioides*

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Manuscript received 30 May 1983, revised 7 December 1983,
accepted 9 March 1984

REINVESTIGATION of the heartwood of *Ougeinia dalbergioides* has yielded genistein, ferreirin, neophellamuretin, orobol and wedelolactone in addition to compounds already reported¹⁻³. This is the first report of the natural occurrence of neophellamuretin in free state and wedelolactone is a rare metabolite. The findings are placed below in Table 1.

TABLE 1—IDENTIFICATION OF COMPOUNDS IN *O. dalbergioides*

Compound isolated	m.p. °C (Solvent of crystallisation)	Literature reference
Homoferreirin	166-67 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	1
Genistein	300 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	5
Ougenin	239-41 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	1
Ferreirin	210-11 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	5
Neophellamuretin	189-91 (EtOAc/petroleum ether)	3
Dalbergiodin	230-32 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	1
Orobol	270-72 (EtOAc)	5
Kaempferol	275-77 (MeOH/CHCl ₃)	2
Wedelolactone	327-30 (MeOH)	4

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The ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of neophellamuretin acetate (Ac₂O/Py) displayed the following peaks (δ): 7.50 (d, 2H, J=8.5Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.18 (d, 2H, J=8.5Hz, H-3', H-5'), 6.62 (s, 1H, H-6), 5.45, 5.75 (2d, 1H each, J=12.5Hz, H-2, H-3), 5.10 (br, 1H, CH of prenyl), 3.25 (d, 2H, J=7.5Hz, CH₂ of prenyl), 2.38 (s, 3H, phenolic acetoxy), 2.32 (s, 6H, two phenolic acetoxy), 2.02 (s, 3H, aliphatic acetoxy), 1.55, 1.68 (2s, 6H, gem methyls). The identity as neophellamuretin was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample of neophellamuretin kindly gifted by Prof. M. Hasegawa who had isolated³ phellamurin (neophellamuretin glycoside) from *Phelladendron amurense* (Rutaceae).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. M. Hasegawa for the gift of neophellamuretin sample, Dr. M. R. Parthasarathy for keen interest in this work and Mr. A. P. Singh for supplying the plant material. One of the authors (S.B.K.) is thankful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Fellowship.

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Solvent Extraction of Uranium(VI) with Versatic 911

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Manuscript received 24 January 1983, revised 15 September 1983, accepted 27 February 1984

CONSIDERABLE interest has developed in recent years on the extraction of metals with high molecular weight carboxylic acids¹. In this communication, a rapid and selective method for the extraction of uranium(VI) with liquid cation exchanger, Versatic 911, in benzene is reported. Uranium(VI) has been quantitatively extracted at pH 5.5-6.0 from 0.1 M acetate solution with 1.81 M Versatic 911. The effect of variables such as pH, diluent, contact time, extractant concentration and acetate ion concentration has been investigated. The organic phase has been stripped with 2 M nitric acid. A probable composition of the extracted species, UO₂R₂.2RH (RH = Versatic 911), has been proposed. The presence of manganese(II), iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II), cadmium(II), silver(I),